

Gender-Based Marginality in Toni Morrison's Beloved

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 1

Month : July

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-2645

Impact Factor: 4.110

Citation:

Kumaresan, R., and
R. Rajeswari. "Gender-
Based Marginality
in Toni Morrison's
Beloved." *Shanlax
International Journal of
English*, vol. 7, no. S1,
2019, pp. 37–40.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.3451764](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3451764)

R.Kumaresan, M.A., M.Phil., B.Ed.,

*Assistant Professor and Head, Department of English
Erode Arts and Science College. (Autonomous), Erode*

Dr.R.Rajeswari, M.A., M.Phil., Ph.D.,

*Assistant Professor and Head, Department of English (SF)
Erode Arts and Science College. (Autonomous), Erode*

Abstract

The focus of this paper is to separate gender issues in literature. It deals with how writers build female characters in their works. Before Shakespeare's period, women characters are notable personalities in literature. This paper mainly focuses on Toni Morrison's female characters through her novel Beloved. Gender defines the behaviour of the individual, how he or she walks, talks, eats and socializes and nearly all other features of everyday life. Gender signifies in the definition of the self. Beloved expresses a black woman who explores the specific ways in how black women suffer. Gender will be examined with a particular allusion to feminism. Feminism as a social philosophy, it shares equal opportunities for career building and self-growth. Feminism is a broad area dealing with the matters of women. Feminism is not only spoken about male domination but also developments of women community. This study is significant for its exclusive focus on the work written by a black woman, her cultural background, her presentation of female characters and their relationships with one another and with male characters. Inequality comes from the rebuttal of equal rights. The main obstacle to equality is sexism. It also examines significant for adopting a female framework for the interpretation of literature written by woman, rather than adopting a male perspective.

Keywords: Gender, Feminism, Refutation, Sexism, Marginality.

The focus of this paper is to analyse gender issues in literature. It deals with how writers build female characters in their works. Before Shakespeare's period, women characters are notable personalities in literature. This paper mainly focuses on Toni Morrison's female characters through her novel Beloved. Gender defines the behaviour of the individual, how he or she walks, talks, eats and socialises and nearly all other features of everyday life. Gender signifies in the definition of the self. Beloved expresses a black woman who explores the specific ways in how black women suffer. Gender will be examined with extraordinary citation to feminism. Feminism as a social philosophy, it shares equal opportunities for career building and self-growth. Feminism is a broad area dispensing with the concerns of women. Feminism is not only spoken about male domination but also developments of women community. This study is significant for its particular focus on the work written by a black

woman, her cultural background, her presentation of female characters and their relationships with one another and with male characters. Inequality comes from the refusal of equal rights. The main obstacle to equality is sexism. It also examines significant for adopting a female framework for the interpretation of literature written by woman, rather than adopting a male perspective.

The relationship between men and women varies in the literature. However, women are generally represented as the marginalized section of society in one way or the other. The role of the man as a dominating figure over woman might be traced back to the ancient pre-historic period. In the Elizabethan period, particularly in the romantic comedies of Shakespeare, female protagonists have been represented as charming and glistening beauty meant exclusively for man's sensual gratification. All the hazardous undertaking is conducted by male characters either for possessing any beautiful and helpless lady or for power and prestige that are not supposed to be in a lot of women. In the nineteenth century, problematic issues of women's marginalization in the patriarchal society were getting the high water mark among a myriad of problems. The Victorian literature, particularly the novels, highlights the emerging image of women. The preoccupation with the place of women was also a recurring theme in the works of the late nineteenth century.

In American literature, particularly in black literature, feminism and racism have played crucial roles. The writers of African American literature would be the base of the events that were taking place in the world around them and consolidate them into their novels. This is the stable and dominant voice in their literature. They have suffered from the attempts of white slave owners to try and erase not only the history of African American but their culture as well.

They had to work; and confer to the aesthetics of this country, they were not beautiful. But neither were they, men. Any intelligence or aggressiveness on their part, qualities necessary for participation in the work world, were constructed as and uninspired (Barbara 72).

The birth of women writers, the growth of female education, the extension of teaching as a female profession and the intensification of a women's literary market are consequently the entire consistent lexis of feminism in a capitalizing global economy. Women writers became an integral part of the literary backdrop, other than until the end of time as representatives of their gender rather than as individuals.

Beloved is Toni Morrison's fifth novel, which published in 1987 as Morrison was taking pleasure in growing popularity and accomplishment. Morrison raises many unanswered topics to think over these pressing issues. What it means to be a mother regularly and what it means to be a mother in slavery. Think about Sethe's relationship with her biological mother, Nan and Baby's relationship with her children and so on.

In Toni Morrison's *Beloved*, she clearly explains gender differences between men and women slaves. Although sometimes the roles overlap, they differ to some extent. As earlier mentioned, Morrison's *Beloved* is a heart-rending story of Sethe, a women slave who escapes the brutality of slave masters at Kentucky to freedom at Cincinnati. Through the eyes of the heroine, her mother and mother-in-law, Babby Suggs, the roles of female slaves are illustrious from those of female slaves such as her husband. Halle and his colleagues like Paul D, Sixo and others. The dehumanizing roles that slaves play cause a deep sense of alienation-estrangement from the self or rather internal fragmentation. Hira Ali observes that *Beloved*'s "fragmented structure" (1442) gives a hint of the characters' sense of alienation that is a consequence of the dehumanizing nature of slavery. Morrison uses some flashbacks that disrupt the chronological order of events.

Beloved represents inter-relatedness among the individual identity and the communal identity of blacks. Stories of two freed slaves, they were Suggs, and Paul D are paralleled to analyze the relations among slaves and master-slave. Resultantly, declaring the need of an individual to retrieve an identity for them before having the bond with the community. In this connection, Morrison

condemns the traditional values associated with white male suppression. She proposes a gender model for blacks based on the mutual suffering of an imprisoned past and struggle for the future of freedom and equality. The battle of black women for the realization of self is eminent in both novels under discussion. It challenges the cultural construction of gender roles by the narrative of two women who are employed in a struggle for the realization of self. In the lives of black woman, brutality makes motherhood a two folded burden. Firstly, they have to view their children who were sold off and experiencing the traumas of slavery. Secondly, most of their children are conceived by rape rather than marital relations. For example, *Beloved* is not a product of hatred, and she wants to want to restrain her from slavery. As Morrison puts, “whites may make her filthy all right, but not her best thing, her beautiful, magical best thing – the part of her that was clean” (*Beloved* 296). Sethe Suggs tries to keep away her children from the impacts of slavery.

The emotional hunger of the child constitutes the essential psychological drama of the novel. An injured, enraged baby is the central figure of the book. It is present in the title character of *Beloved*, and symbolically it is in the unconscious of all the roles of the novel. The viciousness of the baby’s unsatisfied needs, colours, the mother-daughter relationship in *Beloved*. A baby’s unmet needs not only refer to physical needs but also psychic and emotional ones. In *Beloved*, the worst atrocity of slavery and the grimmest dilemma of the novel present not only physical death but also the psychic death. The children have been denied to their basic need and their birthright, which is the lap of the mother that is essential for the psychic growth of the child. This unfulfilled desire leaves such holes in the sub-conscious as are not filled throughout life. Sethe, unable to have the love and care of her mother develops into an overprotective mother whose selfish love takes away the life of her daughter. The predicament, of the novel, is Seth’s murder of her baby daughter, *Beloved*. Seth, having passed the growth of slavery and then able to run away from the cruel master, is on the threshold of being captured again. Her experience of slavery is so worse that she prefers to kill her daughter instead of leaving her to the cruel institution of slavery. So she decides physical death for her daughter instead of psychic death: “if I hadn’t killed her she would have died, and that is something I could not bear to happen to her” (Morrison 1988).

Thus concluding the discussion, it could be said that gender plays a significant role in the construction of self. Due to gender politics, women are doubly oppressed and to combat this oppression first, they have to locate the cause of this oppression and then employ a strategy to deal with it. They have to suffer double persecution, one of patriarchal society and constraints of tradition and the other of the cruel institution of slavery that strips them of every right of motherhood as well as womanhood. Women do exist, and they have played their role in sharing the responsibilities of family and society where men have often shrunk their responsibilities. Especially under the institution of slavery, women have struggled hard to realise their slaves entirely where either their roles as mother or some internal agency catalyse their journey towards the construction of self. Black women, to come to terms with themselves, are fighting for their rights as human beings and as cherished members of the Black society.

Beloved also presents an authoritative account of the foundation of black America in the light of feminism. The ficti, on to some extent recounts the formation of a new people and culture, displaced and forced to forge a unique identity in the face of dehumanization and brutality. It reflects on the subtle balance between individual and community, between self and other. To conclude, feminism is a tool to develop women community, but nowadays, women are thought that feminism is only about male domination. Feminism speaks about women needs, rights, and how they are suppressed in society. The suppression of women is not exclusively male domination but also marginalized culture and religion.

Works Cited

1. Ali, Hira. "Gender Analysis in Toni Morrison's *Beloved* and *Sula*". *Middle Journal of Scientific Research*.16.10.2013.1419-1423. Print.
2. Barbara, Christian. *Black Feminist Criticism: Perspectives on Black Women Writers*. New York. Pergamon Press.1985. Print.
3. Morrison, Toni. *Beloved*, New York. Plume.1988. Print.